

MODELING OF THE SELF-ADJUSTED REACTANT FLOW PATH METHOD FOR CVI OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A model for forming ceramic/ceramic composites based upon the forced-flow, temperature-gradient chemical vapor infiltration method has been proposed. The theoretical analysis has established the relationship among reactant concentration, deposition temperature and pressure. In this study, a self-adjusted-reactant-flow-path method is adopted. The analytical results demonstrate that the reactants alter their path and flow through regions of higher permeability due to the nonhomogeneous deposition within the fibrous preform. As a result, a highly densified ceramic matrix composite can be achieved by controlling the deposition profile through the arrangement of heating elements and by altering the reactant flow pattern. In this analysis, the SiC matrix material is obtained from the thermal decomposition of methyltrichlorosilane gas in excess hydrogen within a fibrous mat. A quasi-steady state approach is adopted to simulate the consolidation of the ceramic composites. It is concluded that a highly densified ceramic/ceramic composite with highly uniform matrix deposition can be achieved by suitable control of the fabrication parameters.

Keywords: chemical vapor infiltration, ceramic composites, modeling, SiC matrix

1. INTRODUCTION

The chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) technique is one of the reaction-based processes for fabricating ceramic-matrix composites. The CVI process, which is an extension of chemical vapor deposition (CVD) methods, involves the transport of gases or vapors in a porous preform and the deposition of the matrix within the preform. Among the existing techniques, the low pressure/isothermal CVI process (ICVI) and the forced-flow/thermal-gradient CVI process (FCVI) which were developed at the University of Bordeaux^[1,2] in France and Oak Ridge National Laboratory^[3,4] in the U.S.A. respectively, are the most well-known.

The isothermal CVI process for ceramic composite involves the infiltration of reactants into a preform through a diffusion process and deposition of the reaction product onto the fiber surface. Deposition gradient of the matrix seems inevitable due to the concentration gradient in an isothermal CVI process. The reopening of the prematurely sealed surface of the preform is one way to enhance the density of the composites. In general, the ICVI process requires an extended processing period. The ability to infiltrate multiple preforms with complex surface contours in a large reactor is a significant advantage of the ICVI process. Theoretical analyses of the ICVI process with a variety of reinforcement structures have been performed during the past few years^[5-7]

In the FCVI process, the fibrous preform is placed in a reactor, and thermal gradient and pressure gradient are imposed within the preform. The processing period is reduced due to the elimination of concentration gradient by the forced flow of reactants within the preform. The temperature gradient in the preform can prevent premature sealing at the inlet surface of the preform. Theoretical analysis of the ORNL experiments has been performed^[8].

In a previous study by the authors, analysis was performed for the infiltration of reactants into a long rectangular preform which is situated in a reactor with pressure and temperature gradients. A "pause and rotation" method was proposed to alleviate the deposition gradient^[9]. According to the analytical results, not only the overall density of the composites can be enhanced but the density distribution also becomes much more uniform. However, the "pause and rotation" method interrupts the processing and alters the preform orientation.

In this work, a self-adjusted-reactant-flow-path (SARFP) method has been proposed, the method involves the infiltration of reactants from two inlets (vapor inlet A and vapor inlet B) into the preform, and the reactants leave the reactor from one outlet (vapor outlet A) in the initial stage, the schematic view of the preform in the reactor is shown in Figure 1. After a period of infiltration, the pressure on one of the inlets (vapor inlet B) is changed to atmospheric pressure so that the reactants change their flow pattern in the preform by entering the reactor from one inlet (vapor inlet A) and leaving the reactor from two outlets (vapor outlet A and vapor outlet B).

The primary objective of this work is to design the flow path for vapor within the preform by suitable arrangement of the heating elements around the reactor in the initial stage of processing. After a period of infiltration and matrix deposition, the flow path can then be automatically adjusted by the deposition gradient of matrix. Therefore, the inlet and outlet of the reactants are located in the same side of the preform. According to the results of theoretical analysis, a highly densified composite can be obtained after applying the SARFP method.

2. THEORETICAL MODELING

For the purpose of simplification of the analytical system, the following assumptions are made:

1. The aspect ratio of the rectangular preform is very large.
2. Reactant flow within the preform obeys Darcy's law.
3. Thermal equilibrium among the matrix, fiber, and reactants in a unit cell is achieved.
4. Deposition is uniform throughout the unit cell.
5. Heat generation by chemical reaction can be neglected.
6. No slip flow at the vapor-solid surface.
7. The density change of the reactants due to the pressure and temperature changes can be determined by the equation of state.

Based upon the assumptions, the equations for the conservation of mass, momentum, energy and species of the present system are summarized as follows.

$$\nabla \cdot \rho \vec{V} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u = -\frac{\kappa}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad v = -\frac{\kappa}{\mu} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} - \rho g \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \rho C_p T \vec{V} = \nabla \cdot K \nabla T \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla \cdot C \vec{V} = \nabla \cdot (D_{12,eff} \nabla C) - R_d A \quad (4)$$

where ∇ denotes the gradient operation, ρ (g/cm³) is the local density of the vapor mixture, \vec{V} (cm/sec) is the local average velocity of the vapor mixtures, u (cm/sec) and v (cm/sec) denote, respectively, the x and y components of the reactant velocity, κ (cm²) is the local permeability of the preform, μ (g/cm·sec) denotes the local viscosity of the vapor mixture, p (g/cm·sec²) is the local pressure, g (cm/sec²) is the gravity acceleration constant, C_p (J/g⁰K) is the specific heat of vapor mixtures, T (°K) is the temperature, and K (Watt/cm⁰K) is the conductivity, C (g/cm³) denotes the concentration of MTS vapor, D (cm²/sec) is the diffusivity of MTS vapor in hydrogen, R_d (moles/cm²·sec) represents the reaction rate of the thermal decomposition of MTS, and A (cm²/cm³) denotes the total deposition surface area in a control volume.

Figure 1 Schematic view of fibrous preform in a FCVI reactor

The chemical reaction in this study is the pyrolysis of methyltrichlorosilane vapor in excess hydrogen. The decomposition reaction is expressed as:

Following the Arrhenius equation and the kinetic deposition data adopted from Ref. [10], the SiC deposition rate, R_d (cm/sec), can be expressed as:

$$R_d = 2.8 \times 10^{-2} [\text{CH}_3\text{SiCl}_3] \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (6)$$

E_a , the activation energy, is 120 kJ/mole for the methyltrichlorosilane decomposition reaction in this study.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, The boundary conditions are varied through the processing. Table 1 gives the boundary conditions for pressure, temperature, and other relevant information. The pressure at the outlet is one atmosphere; on the other hand, the pressure at the inlet is adjusted in order to maintain a constant flow rate of the reactants throughout the preform. After applying the SARFP method, the pressure at inlet B is changed to 1 atm; due to the re-distribution of pressure field within the preform, reactants leave the reactor from outlet A and outlet B. Two cases were studied to examine the influence of temperature on matrix deposition. In Case 1, the temperature of heating elements, holders, and vapor at inlets and outlets remain unchanged throughout the processing; on the other hand, in Case 2, temperatures of vapor inlet A and outlet B are increased to 1223°K and the temperature at holder B is reduced to 1223°K after applying the SARFP method. The boundary conditions for temperature around the preform for the both cases are listed in Table 2.

Figure 2 shows the preform temperature distribution for Case 1 after 25 hours of vapor infiltration. The temperature distribution in the preform is significantly affected by the arrangement of the heating elements around the preform. The maintenance of relatively low temperature at the inlet can prevent the premature pore closure at the vapor entrance. Figure 3 shows density distribution in the preform after 25 hours of vapor infiltration for Case 1. Figure 4 shows density distribution in the preform after 20 hours of vapor infiltration for Case 2. It is very obvious that the final density distribution and processing period are significantly influenced by the temperature boundary conditions.

The maximum theoretical density of 0.805 at the upper left corner (based upon the reference coordinates in Fig. 1) and minimum theoretical density of 0.4746 at the outlet are observed for Case 1. For Case 2, the minimum theoretical density of 0.5729 at the lower right corner is observed at the outlet. Based upon the results, it is concluded that the uniformity of the deposited matrix in preform is enhanced when the SARFP method is applied during processing.

In Case 1, the boundary conditions for temperature is kept unchanged throughout the processing. The relatively low density region at the inlet and outlet is observed; this is due to the relatively low deposition rate at these two regions. On the other hand, the temperatures at the inlet and outlet are increased to 1223 °K and the temperature of holder B is reduced to 1223 °K in Case 2 after applying the SARFP method. Both the uniformity of matrix distribution and average density of composites are enhanced. Furthermore, the infiltration period is reduced. Based upon the analytical results, it is concluded that the a high density composite fabricated by FCVI can be achieved by applying the SARFP method using suitable adjustments of the temperature boundary conditions. The reduction in temperature at the holder B after applying the SARFP method can prevent the premature blocking of the flow channel above holder B.

The influence of reactant concentration on matrix deposition is very limited because the consumption of the reactant is not obvious. The concentration variation within the preform is primarily due to the temperature variation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A model for simulating the forced-flow, temperature-gradient chemical vapor infiltration (FCVI) process has been proposed. In this model, a self-adjusted-reactant-flow-path method is utilized. The matrix distribution, processing period, and uniformity of the deposited matrix are examined in this work. The analytical results demonstrate that the reactants alter their path and flowthrough regions of higher permeability due to the nonhomogeneous deposition within the fibrous preform. As a result, a highly densified ceramic matrix composite can be achieved by controlling the deposition profile through the temperature adjustment of heating elements.

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Figure 2 Temperature distribution in the preform after 25 hours of vapor infiltration for Case 1, number in x and y axes represent the grid points for computational simulation

Table 1 Temperature, pressure, and reactants during processing

	Heating elements	Vapor inlet A	Vapor inlet B	Vapor outlet A	Vapor outlet B	Holder A	Holder B
Temperature (°K)	1273	1123	1123	1273	1123	1273	1273
	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Pressure (atm)	-	1 + ΔP	1 + ΔP	1	-	-	-
	-	1 + ΔP	1 + ΔP	1	1	-	-
Reactants	-	X	X	Y	-	-	-
	-	X	X	Y	Y	-	-

* means no temperature variation through processing.

□ represents parameter conditions after applying the SARFP method.

X denotes the mixtures of CH_3SiCl_3 and H_2

Y denotes the mixtures of CH_3SiCl_3 , H_2 and HCl

Table 2 Temperature of heating elements, holders, and vapor at inlet and outlet for Case 1 and Case 2

	Heating elements	Vapor inlet A	Vapor inlet B	Vapor outlet A	Vapor outlet B	Holder A	Holder B
Case 1	1273	1123	1123	1273	1123	1273	1273
	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Case 2	1273	1123	1123	1273	1123	1273	1273
	*	1223	*	*	1223	*	1223

* means no variation throughout processing.

□ represents parameter conditions after applying the SARFP method.

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Figure 3 Theoretical density distribution in the preform after 25 hours of vapor infiltration for Case 1

Figure 4 Theoretical density distribution in the preform after 20 hours of vapor infiltration for Case 2